

Please, Reboot – Small Economies and the WTO Appellate Mechanism in Times of Trade War and COVID-19

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1. Introduction

When in January 2018, the US government introduced additional tariffs on solar panels and washing machines,¹ only to unilaterally increase tariffs on aluminium and steel shortly thereafter,² a chain of events was set in motion: In their reaction to the allegedly illegal US trade policy decisions, other major economic blocs such as the EU or China disregarded in particular their own procedural obligations under WTO law,³ which may be another symptom of a substantial lack of consensus among major economic powers. A consensus hitherto critical for the functioning of the rules-based global trading system.

About 100 years ago, similar unilateral tariff increases led to a so-called «trade war», which was later proven to have at least deepened the «great depression» that was rampant in the early 1930s.⁴ The GATT Agreement (1947) served in particular to prevent similar escalations of unilateral tariff increases in the future.⁵ For 70 years this goal was indeed achieved. In light of current developments, however, it becomes clear that although the avoidance of trade wars was certainly supported by the GATT (1947)

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¹ See OFFICE OF THE UNITED STATES TRADE REPRESENTATIVE, “President Trump Approves Relief for U.S. Washing Machine and Solar Cell Manufacturers”, press release, 22 January 2018, <<https://ustr.gov/about-us/policy-offices/press-office/press-releases/2018/january/president-trump-approves-relief-us>>.

² See “Presidential Proclamation on Adjusting Imports of Aluminum into the United States”, Donald J. Trump, 8 March 2018, <<https://www.whitehouse.gov/presidential-actions/presidential-proclamation-adjusting-imports-aluminum-united-states/>>; “Presidential Proclamation on Adjusting Imports of Steel into the United States”, Donald J. Trump, 8 March 2018, <<https://www.whitehouse.gov/presidential-actions/presidential-proclamation-adjusting-imports-steel-united-states/>>.

³ For an overview of trade policy measures implemented worldwide since 2018, see CHAD P. BOWN/MELINA KOLB, Trump’s Trade War Timeline: An Up-to-Date Guide, PIIE, <<https://www.piie.com/blogs/trade-investment-policy-watch/trump-trade-war-china-date-guide>>.

⁴ ANDREW LANG, *World Trade Law After Neoliberalism: Reimagining the Global Economic Order*, New York, 2011, 191-2.

⁵ LANG, 196-7.

and later by the WTO Agreements, it was primarily based on a fundamental consensus among GATT/WTO members on the usefulness of common multilateral trade rules.

The fact that the major economic blocs today no longer agree on which rules should apply in global trade reveals weaknesses in the WTO system and leads to the (temporary) downgrading of the WTO from a law enforcement agency to an administrator. This paper takes a closer look at the legal protection of trade interests of small and independent economies before the crisis in multilateralism and discusses to what extent the heavy dependence of the rules-based trading system on consensus among major economic blocs may have contributed to its current crises. It then turns to exploring alternative instruments for the legal protection of trade interests of small and independent economies outside of the WTO system, and to – from the perspective of small and independent economies – most critical practical and legal shortfalls in the previous WTO dispute settlement system, which ought to be addressed in the interest of all WTO members when considering re-establishing the WTO appellate mechanism in international trade disputes.

2. Relevant Terms

The world is currently facing a number of unprecedented challenges. Aside from the global COVID-19 pandemic, the global market had already been disrupted by trade disputes between major economic blocs prior to the outbreak of the Corona-virus. This disruption was in parts based on actual trade policy decisions by a number of WTO members, the overall result of which may be called a «trade war». On the other hand, this «trade war» may ultimately only be a symptom of a more serious condition of which the global trading system has been suffering for a while already; a lack of «global consensus». Small and independent economies have always been structurally more vulnerable to economic damage due to unfavourable trade policy decisions by large economies. The current developments exacerbate their vulnerability. Given that these terms have particular relevance to the assessment of current events, it is critical to first establish what phenomenae this paper refers to.

a. Trade War

Not every trade dispute reaches the intensity of a «trade war». While international economic law seeks in particular to prevent «trade wars» from happening, it explicitly recognises the occurrence of trade disputes and provides for a legal and institutional framework for their resolution. The distinction between «trade war» and «trade dispute» is therefore quite relevant.

WTO law does not provide for its own definition of «trade war». «Trade war» is sometimes described analogously as an attempt by a state to gain economic advantages while harming other states through customs duties and quota restrictions.⁶ This definition could, strictly speaking, cover the majority of trade disputes worldwide. Such events are explicitly called «trade disputes» in WTO-law. They typically deal with a particular disagreement on a specific, definable legal issue that can be resolved by judges or arbitrators or at the negotiating table. Hence, it would seem more appropriate to distinguish between «trade war» and «trade disputes» by means of *e contrario* analysis between measures which are covered by the WTO Dispute Settlement Understanding (DSU), and measures which are not. Hence,

⁶ Regarding the definition of «trade war», see e.g. NIK MARTIN, «Wann wird ein Streit zum Handelskrieg?», DW.com, 6 July 2018, <<https://www.dw.com/de/wann-wird-ein-streit-zum-handelskrieg/a-44463416>>. There is no one, common definition of «trade war» to be found in literature. Depending on the author and the respective area, the two terms «trade war» and «trade dispute» are used in a variety of ways.

temporal and political characteristics, in addition to the aforementioned characteristics of a trade dispute, have been applied in order to differentiate between a «trade dispute» and a «trade war».

Accordingly, a «trade war» consists here (cumulatively) in 1) a never-ending series of customs levies and quota restrictions with the aim of harming other states and thereby gaining trade advantages for themselves or asserting political interests. And, in 2) an unspecified, undefineable dissatisfaction with the rules/*status quo*.⁷

Thus, «trade war» differs from trade dispute in terms of the time dimension (the never-ending series of customs levies and quota restrictions) and the political dimension (no single, clearly identifiable cause). Hence, because it clearly deals with an identifiable cause, the US-EU dispute over subsidies to Airbus and Boeing respectively, for example, which has been going on for several years now, does not qualify as «trade war» – even though it might indeed seem never-ending.⁸

This delimitation appears to be sensible in the light of WTO law, which explicitly recognises and names the occurrence of trade disputes and provides the necessary legal recourse to clarify specific, delimitable legal questions. In sum, a «trade war» is an escalation in a trade dispute which is no longer comprehensively covered by the available legal channels.⁹

b. «Global Consensus» in the Context of International Economic Law

Here, reference to indications of a «lost consensus» is not directly related to the WTO's decision-making process.¹⁰ Rather what is referred to in this context here, is the nature of the underlying consensus regarding the benefits of mutually binding international trade rules. The original consensus on which the applicable WTO rules rely upon – emerging from a general shift toward integration and legalisation in trade liberalisation – was based on the fact that economic integration was understood to be a driver of economic growth, a guarantor of peace, and that legalisation of international economic relations was meant to depoliticise international economic transactions.¹¹ Consequently, WTO members complied (more or less) with the rules established in the WTO Agreements voluntarily. Disagreements were in large parts solved through the WTO dispute settlement proceedings, while compliance with rulings of the WTO dispute settlement body was extraordinarily high.

As is well-documented elsewhere,¹² this underlying consensus is in distress. WTO members no longer comply most of the time and voluntarily with the rules established in the WTO Agreements and resolution of disagreements between WTO members is increasingly sought (semi-)outside of the WTO dispute settlement proceedings. In parts, this is linked with the nature of the applicable multilateral trade rules which – as some argue – have led to adverse outcomes and urgently require revision. It is also linked with procedural and institutional aspects of the WTO dispute settlement system, and the inability of the WTO system to fully integrate state-capitalistic members like China. What is of particular interest here, are the procedural and institutional aspects of the WTO dispute settlement system, which may

⁷ Definition *e contrario* Article 1 WTO Dispute Settlement Understanding (DSU), 1 July 1995.

⁸ See *European Communities and Certain Member States – Measures Affecting Trade in Large Civil Aircraft*, DS316, since 2004; *United States – Measures Affecting Trade in Large Civil Aircraft*, Second complaint, DS353, since 2005.

⁹ Such as defined in the DSU.

¹⁰ Regarding the concept of «consensus» in the WTO decision-making process, see e.g. WENWEI GUAN, 'Consensus Yet Not Consented: A Critique of the WTO Decision-Making by Consensus', *JIEL*, vol. 17, 77-104.

¹¹ FRANCESCO MONTANARO/FEDERICA VIOLI, 'The Remains of the Day: The International Economic Order in the Era of Disintegration', *JIEL*, vol. 23, 299-322, 304-5.

¹² See for example Special Issue 'The Era of Disintegration – Taking Stock of the Dynamics of International Economic Governance', *JIEL*, no. 2, vol. 23, June 2020.

play a critical role in the on-going erosion of the global consensus regarding the benefits and scope of multilateral trade rules.

Arguably, small and independent economies have always been aware of the institutional and procedural disadvantages embedded in the WTO Agreements, since they were more affected by them than large economic blocs. For small and independent economies, the benefits of WTO membership – aside from the points mentioned above – were also accruing from the stability and protection against power politics embedded in the fact that large economic blocs were willing to comply with the rules voluntarily. Given that this is no longer always the case, WTO membership may likely be re-assessed sooner or later also by small and independent economies.

c. Small and Independent Economies

Small and independent economies are used here as a proxy for WTO members which are 1) small in terms of economic power (not near the top 10 of global GDP per capita rankings), and 2) independent in the design, implementation and enforcement of their foreign trade policy (e.g. not a member of the EU). Obviously, this group of countries encompasses the majority of WTO members,¹³ and therewith considerable diversity in terms of geographic, political, social and economic conditions. Nevertheless, it is argued here, that this large group of WTO members is unified 1) in their relative dependence on export, 2) in their deep integration in global value chains, and 3) in their inability to effectively enforce policy-change *via* retaliatory measures.

3. Implications for Small and Independent Economies

If we are indeed in times of «trade war» and at loss of a «global consensus» regarding the benefits and the general scope of multilateral trade rules (and the compliance therewith), this has decidedly different implications for small and independent economies than it has for large economic blocs. Nevertheless, what happened in the past three or so years may actually be a symptom of the fact that what small and independent economies had to accept from the very beginning of the establishment of the GATT (1947) and later the WTO – dealing with power imbalances and institutional and legal oversights – has become visible – and perceptible – also to the large economic blocs. Possibly, the identification of legal and institutional implications of trade war and a lost global consensus for small and independent economies may therefore also be of relevance to WTO members in their entirety.

a. Review of the Events of the Past Three Years

The US trade deficit was already a major issue in the 2016 US presidential election campaign, especially in the campaign of the then candidate Donald J. Trump. His «Jobs Plan» included the assessment that politicians had aggressively pursued a policy of globalization and therewith moved jobs and wealth to Mexico and overseas. Furthermore, foreign countries had violated their agreements and cheated in every way imaginable, which turned out to be a «politician-made disaster» for Americans. Trump promised to use every tool and presidential power under American and international law available to end these alleged abuses.¹⁴

¹³ For a detailed discussion of the diversity among WTO members, see e.g. CHARLOTTE SIEBER-GASSER, *Developing Countries and Preferential Services Trade*, Cambridge University Press, 2016, 4ff.

¹⁴ See «Full transcript: Donald Trump's jobs plan speech», politico.com, 28 June 2016, <<https://www.politico.com/story/2016/06/full-transcript-trump-job-plan-speech-224891>>.

One of the first official acts of the newly elected US President Donald J. Trump in early 2017 was indeed – among others – the termination of US membership in the Trans-Pacific Trade Agreement (TPP).¹⁵ Furthermore, Trump gave the mandate to the US Department of Trade to review the threat to national security posed by the US trade deficit¹⁶ and announced the intention to renegotiate the NAFTA agreement.¹⁷ In his first year in office, further measures were taken in order to limit the influence of the WTO on US trade policy, such as the *de facto* boycott of the WTO Ministerial Conference in Argentina in December 2017 or the blockage of appointments of judges to the WTO Appellate Body (AB).¹⁸ In line with these policy measures, in early 2018 a series of unilateral tariffs as well as punitive tariffs against China were introduced.

First, the US government unilaterally increased tariffs on solar cells and washing machines in January 2018.¹⁹ South Korea challenged both measures at the WTO,²⁰ while China only challenged the additional tariffs on solar cells.²¹ Other interested parties joined the complaints as third parties. The decisions are pending. In early March 2018, Trump announced that, as a measure to protect national security, he would unilaterally increase customs duties on aluminium and steel by 10% and 25% respectively by presidential decree.²² The suspicion that the US trade deficit in aluminium and steel poses a threat to national security because it affected the defence industry had previously been confirmed in the investigation commission under Section 232 of the US Trade Expansion Act (1962).²³ This decision led to a chain reaction around the globe. For example, a number of WTO members lodged complaints at the WTO.²⁴ In addition, several WTO members, including the EU, Turkey, China, India,

¹⁵ «Presidential Memorandum Regarding Withdrawal of the United States from the Trans-Pacific Partnership Negotiations and Agreement», Presidential Memoranda, 23 January 2017, <<https://www.whitehouse.gov/presidential-actions/presidential-memorandum-regarding-withdrawal-united-states-trans-pacific-partnership-negotiations-agreement/>>.

¹⁶ «President Donald J. Trump: Standing up to Unfair Steel Trade Practices», Fact Sheets, 20 April 2017, <<https://www.whitehouse.gov/briefings-statements/president-donald-j-trump-standing-unfair-steel-trade-practices/>>.

¹⁷ OFFICE OF THE UNITED STATES TRADE REPRESENTATIVE, «USTR: Trump Administration Announces Intent to Renegotiate the North American Free Trade Agreement», Press Release, 18 May 2017, <<https://ustr.gov/about-us/policy-offices/press-office/press-releases/2017/may/ustr-trump-administration-announces>>.

¹⁸ See e.g. OFFICE OF THE UNITED STATES TRADE REPRESENTATIVE, «The President’s 2017 Trade Policy Agenda», Annual Report, 1 March 2017, <<https://ustr.gov/sites/default/files/files/reports/2017/AnnualReport/Chapter%20I%20-%20The%20President%27s%20Trade%20Policy%20Agenda.pdf>>; PHIL LEVY, «2017: Trump’s Troubled Year In Trade Policy», forbes.com, 29 December 2017, <<https://www.forbes.com/sites/phillevy/2017/12/29/2017-trade-year-in-review/#21411a19482b>>.

¹⁹ OFFICE OF THE UNITED STATES TRADE REPRESENTATIVE, «Section 201 Cases: Imported Large Residential Washing Machines and Imported Solar Cells and Modules», Factsheet, 22 January 2018, <<https://ustr.gov/sites/default/files/files/Press/fs/201%20FactSheet.pdf>>.

²⁰ Decision pending: *United States – Safeguard Measure on Imports of Large Residential Washers*, DS546; *United States – Safeguard Measure on Imports of Crystalline Silicon Photovoltaic Products*, DS545.

²¹ Decision pending: *United States – Safeguard Measure on Imports of Crystalline Silicon Photovoltaic Products*, DS562.

²² See “Presidential Proclamation on Adjusting Imports of Aluminum into the United States”, Donald J. Trump, 8 March 2018, <<https://www.whitehouse.gov/presidential-actions/presidential-proclamation-adjusting-imports-aluminum-united-states/>>; “Presidential Proclamation on Adjusting Imports of Steel into the United States”, Donald J. Trump, 8 March 2018, <<https://www.whitehouse.gov/presidential-actions/presidential-proclamation-adjusting-imports-steel-united-states/>>.

²³ WILBUR ROSS, «Remarks by Secretary Wilbur Ross at the White House», U.S. Department of Commerce, 27 April 2017, <<https://www.commerce.gov/issues/trade-enforcement/section-232-aluminum#remarks>>.

²⁴ Decisions still pending: *United States – Certain Measures on Steel and Aluminium Products*, DS544 (China), DS547 (India), DS548 (EU), DS552 (Norway), DS554 (Russia), DS556 (Switzerland), and DS564 (Turkey). The two complaints by Mexico (DS551) and Canada (DS550) were dropped as exemptions were agreed to as part of negotiations over the modernisation of NAFTA.

Mexico and Canada, imposed additional duties on selected US imports as a countermeasure under Article 8 of the WTO Agreement on Safeguards (SG Agreement). This was again challenged by the US at the WTO.²⁵ The decisions are pending.

In the meantime – and at the early outbreak of the 2020 global pandemic – the US already implemented further tariff increases on aluminium and steel products in order to counteract the alleged circumvention of their previous tariff increases.²⁶ In reaction to these additional tariffs, the EU introduced in April 2020 additional retaliatory duties on selected US products.²⁷ In August 2020, finally, the US introduced a 10% «national security» tariff on aluminium from Canada.²⁸ Canada in return announced retaliatory tariffs on US aluminium products in the same week.²⁹

In addition to the unilaterally imposed tariffs on aluminium and steel, the US filed WTO complaints against China for violation of intellectual property obligations,³⁰ and against India for prohibited export subsidies,³¹ in March 2018. Without waiting for the WTO dispute settlement ruling, the US then imposed additional tariffs on a range of Chinese imported goods from July 2018 as a kind of countermeasure to the alleged intellectual property theft.³² In turn, China imposed additional tariffs on selected US products, also in July 2018, and filed a WTO complaint against the US tariffs.³³ A second round of further reciprocal tariff increases followed in August 2018, against which China lodged an additional complaint at the WTO.³⁴ Finally, a third round of reciprocal tariff increases followed in September 2018, although no further complaints were initially lodged at the WTO. An interim standstill in the adoption of further reciprocal trade sanctions was finally negotiated in December 2018.³⁵ Further negotiations between China and the US were, however, unsuccessful, hence, in May 2019, the US again increased tariffs on selected products from China. In addition to the tariff increases and the pending WTO complaints against China, the US also placed Huawei and its subsidiaries on the blacklist of

²⁵ Decisions pending: *China – Additional Duties on Certain Products from the United States* (DS558), *European Union – Additional Duties on Certain Products from the United States* (DS559), *Turkey – Additional Duties on Certain Products from the United States* (DS561), *Russian Federation – Additional Duties on Certain Products from the United States* (DS566), *India – Additional Duties on Certain Products from the United States* (DS585). The two complaints against Mexico (DS560) and Canada (DS557) were dropped as agreement was reached as part of negotiations over the modernisation of NAFTA.

²⁶ «Proclamation on Adjusting Imports of Derivative Aluminum Articles and Derivative Steel Articles into the United States», Proclamations, 24 January 2020, <<https://www.whitehouse.gov/presidential-actions/proclamation-adjusting-imports-derivative-aluminum-articles-derivative-steel-articles-united-states/>>.

²⁷ Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2020/502, 6 April 2020.

²⁸ See for a comment e.g. MARC L. BUSCH, «Trump’s tariffs on Canada are about more than aluminium», Atlantic Council, 11 August 2020, <<https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/blogs/new-atlanticist/trumps-tariffs-on-canada-are-about-more-than-aluminum/>>.

²⁹ See e.g. BBC, «Canada slaps retaliatory tariffs on US aluminium goods», 7 August 2020, <<https://www.bbc.com/news/world-us-canada-53683569>>.

³⁰ *China – Certain Measures concerning the Protection of Intellectual Property Rights*, DS542. The panel has been suspended due to on-going bilateral negotiations between the US and China, Communication from the Panel, 5 March 2020, WT/DS542/12. Parallel negotiations between US, EU, Japan and China are taking place regarding mandatory technology transfer, see *China – Certain Measures on the Transfer of Technology*, DS549. For further information see JULIA YA QIN, *Forced Technology Transfer and the US-China Trade War: Implications for International Economic Law*, Wayne State University Law School Legal Studies Research Paper Series No. 2019-61, 2019, <https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3436974>.

³¹ *India – Export related Measures*, Report of the Panel, 31 October 2019, WT/DS541/R. India appealed the decision which is now pending before the AB.

³² Based on the investigations under Section 301 US Trade Act of 1974.

³³ *United States – Tariff Measures on Certain Goods from China*, DS543.

³⁴ *United States – Tariff Measures on Certain Goods from China II*, DS565.

³⁵ «Statement from the Press Secretary Regarding the President’s Working Dinner with China», Whitehouse Press Briefing, 1 December 2018, <<https://www.whitehouse.gov/briefings-statements/statement-press-secretary-regarding-presidents-working-dinner-china/>>.

companies that violate US security interests.³⁶ Further Chinese companies were added to the list in summer 2019. As a result, further increases by China on US products came into force in June 2019. Finally, in September 2019 – after the US officially accused China of currency manipulation – further tariff increases were implemented and China lodged yet another complaint against these US tariffs at the WTO.³⁷

After both the US and China submitted lists of products that are exempted from additional tariffs in the same month, negotiations proceeded and finally resulted in a joint «trade pact» and the signing of the so-called «Phase One Deal» in January 2020.³⁸ In this deal, the US and China agree to refrain from further increasing tariffs against each other. A meeting to evaluate the deal in August 2020 was cancelled by the US after China had suspended purchases of US goods as agreed in the deal due to – and contrary to what was agreed in the «Phase One Deal» – the introduction of additional US tariffs on Chinese goods.³⁹ Later that month, the US and China nevertheless reaffirmed their willingness to implement the «Phase One Deal».⁴⁰ Due to pandemic-related economic reasons and politics set aside, it remains uncertain whether it will be possible to fully implement the «Phase One Deal». It is also uncertain at this point, whether the «Phase One Deal» is compatible with WTO obligations, since it is clearly not a Preferential Trade Agreement (PTA) and does, hence, not qualify under the exceptions in Article XXIV GATT or Article V GATS. Depending on the legal character of the tariff reductions and «purchases» agreed to, the «Phase One Deal» may actually in particular violate Most-Favoured Nation (MFN) obligations of both the US and China.

The additional US-tariffs on selected Chinese products have their origin in the US Department of Commerce investigation into unfair trade practices under Section 301 of the 1974 Trade Act.⁴¹ Unilateral measures taken under Section 301 of the Trade Act 1974 had already be found incompatible with Article 23 DSU in 1999 in a WTO dispute. In particular, the panel stated that WTO members may not unilaterally take trade measures against other WTO members without prior recourse to the WTO procedures provided for this purpose.⁴² The US accepted the panel ruling at the time and added an instruction to that effect under Section 301 of the Trade Act 1974 in the context of the dispute settlement procedure.⁴³ The additional US-tariffs on selected Chinese products therefore stand in direct

³⁶ Based on the International Emergency Economic Powers Act, see «Executive Order on Securing the Information and Communications Technology and Services Supply Chain», Executive Orders, 15 May 2019, <<https://www.whitehouse.gov/presidential-actions/executive-order-securing-information-communications-technology-services-supply-chain/>>.

³⁷ *United States – Tariff Measures on Certain Goods from China III*, DS587.

³⁸ Economic and Trade Agreement between the Government of the United States of America and the Government of the People's Republic of China, 20 January 2020, <https://ustr.gov/sites/default/files/files/agreements/phase%20one%20agreement/Economic_And_Trade_Agreement_Between_The_United_States_And_China_Text.pdf>.

³⁹ See e.g. The Brussels Times, «Trump cancels US-China trade negotiations», 19 August 2020, <<https://www.brusselstimes.com/news/belgium-all-news/130136/mrs-bouchez-wants-sophie-wilmes-to-stay-on-after-16-september/>>.

⁴⁰ Office of the United States Trade Representative, «Statement on Call Between the United States and China», 24 August 2020, <<https://ustr.gov/about-us/policy-offices/press-office/press-releases/2020/august/statement-call-between-united-states-and-china>>.

⁴¹ Office of the United States Trade Representative, «Findings of the Investigation into China's Acts, Policies, and Practices related to Technology Transfer, Intellectual Property, and Innovation Under Section 301 of the Trade Act of 1974», 22 March 2018, <<https://ustr.gov/sites/default/files/Section%20301%20FINAL.PDF>>, 5.

⁴² *United States – Sections 301-310 of the Trade Act 1974*, 28. Februar 2000, WT/DS152/14, para. 7.97; see also JENS LEHNE, *Crisis at the WTO: Is the Blocking of Appointments to the WTO Appellate Body by the United States Legally Justified?*, in: Daniel Hürlimann/Marc Thommen (eds.), *sui generis*, Band 6, 2019, 127.

⁴³ See CAITLAIN DEVEREAUX LEWIS, «Tricks of the Trade: Section 301 Investigation of Chinese Intellectual Property Practices Concludes (Part I)», Congressional Research Services, LSB10108, 29 March 2018, 3-4.

contradiction with both US WTO obligations and established WTO case-law. PATCH describes the significance of the thus intentional breach of WTO obligations as follows:⁴⁴

The resulting climate, where countries will feel they can ignore the WTO framework, not only has near-term implications, it also threatens to destroy the long-term economic integration that followed the creation of [GATT/]WTO post-World War II.

In the wake of the COVID-19 outbreak some of these bilateral tariffs were abandoned. For example, US tariffs on selected Chinese medical products were temporarily eliminated in March 2020.⁴⁵ China on the other hand already exempted a range of American products from the additional tariffs, currently this exemption remains limited to one year.⁴⁶ This possible pandemic-related interruption of the never-ending series of additional tariffs may, however, not hide the fact that the conditions for a «trade war» are indeed fulfilled. It is unclear at this stage whether the global economic crisis of the next few years will lead to an easing of the trade war – and consequently it is also unclear whether the trade war has thus ended or whether it will flare up again all the more violently once the immediate threat of life from the virus has been averted.

In sum, we have witnessed in the past three years an escalation of tariff increases around the globe and by various WTO members, based on questionable legal justification. We have also witnessed the temporary inoperability of the AB, along with the first two WTO members appealing Panel decisions in full awareness that they are therewith sending the verdict into a legal void.⁴⁷ At the same time, pending disputes at the WTO mount up to impressive figures,⁴⁸ *alas* whether Panel decisions will ultimately be accepted by the parties remains very uncertain. More recently, WTO members have turned to bilateral negotiations – outside of the WTO forum – to, among others, negotiate tariff eliminations on an MFN basis.⁴⁹ Whether these will later be notified to the WTO remains uncertain at this time. It can, thus, be concluded that we are finding ourselves in a time of a trade war, potentially the symptom of an underlying lack of global consensus regarding the benefit and scope of multilateral trade rules. This lack of the rule of law in the global market incentivises trade policies of a more mercantilist nature.

b. Review of impact for small and independent economies

By embedding local production in global value chains, unilateral or even bilateral measures taken by other countries quickly have an impact on production in small economies: Every tariff increase affecting a single component or production site within the global value chain has an impact on the final price

⁴⁴ COLIN PATCH, A Unilateral President vs. A Multilateral Trade Organization: Ethical Implications In The Ongoing Trade War, *The Georgetown Journal of Legal Ethics*, vol. 32, 883-902, 897.

⁴⁵ Federal Register, vol. 85, No. 58, 25 March 2020, Notices, 16987ff.

⁴⁶ MINISTRY OF FINANCE OF THE PEOPLE'S REPUBLIC OF CHINA, Announcement of the State Council Tariff Commission regarding the Second Exemption List of Tariffs regarding the United States and Canada Tax Commission Announcement, 21 February 2020, <http://gss.mof.gov.cn/gzdt/zhengcefabu/202002/t20200221_3472600.htm>.

⁴⁷ *Saudi Arabia – Measures Concerning the Protection of Intellectual Property Rights (DS567)*, Notification of an appeal by the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, 28 July 2020, WT/DS567/7, and *EU – Cost Adjustment Methodologies and Certain Anti-Dumping Measures (DS494)*, WTO ‘EU appeals panel report report on EU dumping methodologies, dues on Russian imports’, 28 August 2020, <https://www.wto.org/english/news_e/news20_e/ds494apl_28aug20_e.htm>.

⁴⁸ Since January 2018 alone, 61 complaints have been filed, 56 are still pending. See also WTO, Chronological list of disputes cases, <https://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/dispu_e/dispu_status_e.htm>.

⁴⁹ See e.g. European Commission, Joint Statement of the United States and the European Union on a Tariff Agreement, 21 August 2020, <<https://trade.ec.europa.eu/doclib/press/index.cfm?id=2178>>.

along the entire value chain. The export industry of small economies is therefore particularly vulnerable to losses as a result of individual preferential or protectionist measures in the global market.

The bilateral additional tariffs between China and the US, the unilateral additional US-tariffs on aluminium and steel along with retaliatory and safeguard measures by other WTO members in reaction to the US-tariffs on steel and aluminium thus all also affect local production and exports in small economies. Tariff increases and quotas have, however, a delayed effect on global value chains and economic growth. Economists expected therefore, that the negative economic impact on the global market and thus also on small economies of the bilateral tariff increases between the US and China would not peak until mid-2021.⁵⁰ In the meantime, the impact of the trade war on small and independent economies is likely to be overshadowed multiple times by the effects of the pandemic-related interruption of the global economy in 2020.

Hence, although not directly involved in the disputes and bilateral and unilateral increases of tariffs, small and independent economies have been affected by the trade war of the recent years. The economic damage was in early 2020 only expected to become fully visible in 2021; in the meantime, the global pandemic has further impacted on global value chains and export-industries of small and independent economies while they will continue to depend on global value chains and their export-industries in their economic recovery.

c. Time-lag between violation and remedy

The Chinese countermeasures against the additional US-tariffs on selected Chinese products violate the same Article 23.2 DSU as did the original US-tariffs under Section 301 of the Trade Act 1974: China would have been obliged to wait for the WTO ruling before taking countermeasures. In the current DS542 complaint case, the US is therefore defending itself, *inter alia*, by referring to the Chinese countermeasures already in force:⁵¹

In sum: China already has taken self-help in the form of tariff measures, and other retaliatory measures, affecting most U.S. exports. At most, DSB findings on the U.S. tariff measures would provide China with a public relations point [...]. China's pursuit of this dispute cannot be seen as anything other than an attempted misuse of the system.

QIN therefore rightly asks whether it would not have served China's economic interests better to wait for the WTO panel's decision first. In all likelihood, China would have been successful in the complaint against US-tariffs and would have been able to impose appropriate sanctions following the panel ruling. In the meantime, however, US tariffs on Chinese products would likely have remained at the original level of March 2018 and the escalation of tariff increases would not have occurred, an escalation which remains harmful to the entire global market.⁵² The question remains whether those initial US-tariffs on Chinese goods would have affected Chinese exports to the US substantially – and therewith caused

⁵⁰ BEN HOLLAND/CEDRIC SAM, «A 600 Billion Bill: Counting the Global Cost of the U.S.-China Trade War», Bloomberg, 27 May 2019, <<https://www.bloomberg.com/graphics/2019-us-china-trade-war-economic-fallout/>>; WORLD BANK, «Global Economic Prospects: Slow Growth, Policy Challenges», Washington, 2020, 8-11.

⁵¹ First Written Submission of the United States of America, *United States – Tariff Measures on Certain Goods from China*, DS543, <<https://ustr.gov/sites/default/files/enforcement/DS/US.Sub1.%28DS543%29.fin.%28public%29.pdf>>, para. 59.

⁵² JULIA QIN, «US-China Tariff War: A Lesson about WTO Law», International Economic Law and Policy Blog, 11. September 2019, <<https://ielp.worldtradelaw.net/2019/09/us-china-tariff-war-a-lesson-about-wto-law.html>>.

economic damage to China –, and whether the US would indeed have stopped at the level of the initial tariffs and waited for the panel decision before taking additional measures against China.

From filing a complaint until an initial WTO panel decision is taken, it usually takes up to two years. However, the economic damage already occurs as soon as the measure in question enters into force. This two year «waiting period» for countermeasures (or safeguard measures as in the case of the US-tariffs on steel and aluminium) may therefore be sufficient to achieve the desired protective effect in individual cases; following a possibly foreseeable panel decision, the disputed measure could then be revoked and countermeasures would no longer have to be feared.⁵³ Should a trade measure be found unlawful and be corrected thereafter, at least it no longer increases the damage – but such correction does not either remedy the damage which took place in the time between the implementation of the measure and its end. Depending on the structure of the export industry affected, recovery from the economic damage poses a greater challenge for a small economy than for a large and thus less specialised and less export-oriented economy (and therewith has broader economic side effects).

Hence, small and independent economies have always been more at risk of substantial economic damage due to the inherent waiting period in the WTO dispute settlement proceedings.

d. Safeguards

While Liechtenstein, as a member of the EEA, is in principle exempted from EU safeguard measures in response to the unilateral US tariffs on aluminium and steel, Switzerland is also affected by EU safeguard tariffs in addition to US tariffs.⁵⁴ The EU introduced safeguard tariffs in 2019, which will take effect once the quotas on steel imports are exhausted.⁵⁵ So far, – also thanks to the drop in demand – the quotas are sufficient to allow Switzerland to continue exporting to the EU without additional protective tariffs, while accepting additional administrative costs.⁵⁶

From the EU's point of view, it became necessary to protect the EU market against cheap imports from China because the unilateral US tariffs led to trade diversion. According to Article 2.2 SG Agreement, such measures must in principle be adopted unilaterally and irrespective of the origin of a product. They therefore also affect small and independent economies and their local production. The impact of such unilateral safeguard measures depends to a greater or lesser extent on the importance of the market concerned for the export industry concerned. As the vast majority of Swiss exports of steel products (95%) go to the EU, the potential impact of the EU protective tariffs necessitated by the US measures on Switzerland is therefore much greater than the original unilateral US-tariffs were.

⁵³ See for example in a related discussion THOMAS COTTIER, *Renewable Energy and WTO Law: More Policy Space or Enhanced Disciplines?*, RELP 1/2014, 40-51, 44: «The Time it takes to challenge and adjudicate such measures may be sufficient to protect an infant industry and to establish a viable industry even after the requirement will be eventually removed.»

⁵⁴ Regarding the status of bilateral negotiations between the EU and Switzerland on safeguard measures, see STAATSSSEKRETARIAT FÜR WIRTSCHAFT SECO, «EU-Massnahmen auf Stahl- und Aluminiumimporten», last updated 4 December 2019, <https://www.seco.admin.ch/seco/de/home/Aussenwirtschaftspolitik_Wirtschaftliche_Zusammenarbeit/Wirtschaftsbeziehungen/handelsschutzmassnahmen/EU_schutzmassnahmen_stahl.html>.

⁵⁵ Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2019/159 of 31 January 2019.

⁵⁶ «Schweizer Aluminiumindustrie: Leichtes Plus in 2018 – Gute Aussichten für 2019», Packaktuell.ch, 29 March 2019, <<https://www.packaktuell.ch/newspool/schweizer-aluminiumindustrie-leichtes-plus-in-2018-gute-aussichten-fuer-2019/>>; MELANIE LOOS, «Wie der Handelsstreit den Schweizer Mittelstand trifft», Handelszeitung, 27 August 2019, <<https://www.handelszeitung.ch/konjunktur/wie-der-handelsstreit-den-schweizer-mittelstand-trifft>>.

On the other hand, Switzerland (and other small and independent economies for that matter) are unlikely to often endeavour to protect their own industries *via* safeguards: Protective measures in the form of quotas and unilateral tariff increases are much more likely to affect their own companies and consumers than effectively protect the respective industries. This is for the simple reason that small and independent economies are more dependent on the supply of raw materials and components than large economies. Hence, there is always a risk that protective measures will primarily harm domestic production in small and independent economies. This may, for instance, partly explain why Switzerland has not yet taken any WTO safeguard measures.

Hence, the design of safeguard measures – unilateral in general, limited to tariffs and quotas – rendered them a rather void for small and independent economies from the start: Applying tariffs and quotas in order to protect an industry is likely to cause more economic damage in small and independent economies than it is likely to effectively protect vulnerable industries.

e. Retaliation

Clearly controversial are the countermeasures against selected American products which have been taken by the EU and other WTO members on the basis of Article 8 SG Agreement. It is questionable whether this was permissible before the WTO decision was taken, since it had not yet been established by the WTO dispute settlement body whether the US tariffs are to be regarded as protective measures – or whether they fall within the exemption in Article XXI GATT. Again, the obligation derived from Article 23.2 DSU, to refrain from unilateral countermeasures until the dispute settlement proceedings have been completed, applies.⁵⁷

It is remarkable that other WTO members have been tempted to potentially violate their obligations under Article 23 DSU. For example, the EU would be institutionally obliged not to take any action that is contrary to WTO law. The fact that the allegedly WTO incompatible countermeasures of the EU and other WTO members have led to little or no contradiction therefore speaks for the political backing of this «tit-for-tat» trade policy, which actually is explicitly declared illegal by WTO law.⁵⁸

One critical aspect here is the scope of Article 8 SG Agreement: If a measure falls within the scope of Article 8 SG Agreement, it is in principle still possible to take countermeasures without a legally binding panel decision. This is because Article 8 SG Agreement grants the injured party such a right if negotiations on appropriate trade compensation fail. However, if – as in the case of the additional US-tariffs on aluminium and steel – it is disputed whether the trade measures in question constitute a safeguard measure, it must first be clarified whether Article 8 SG Agreement applies at all. This can only be established via the general WTO dispute settlement proceedings.⁵⁹

Just like in the case of safeguard measures – the same applies to retaliation for small and independent economies: there is a risk, even in bilateral relations, that tariff increases in the context of

⁵⁷ See also CHRISTOPH HERRMANN/CAROLINE GLÖCKLE, Der drohende transatlantische “Handelskrieg» um Stahlerzeugnisse und das handelspolitische «Waffenarsenal» der EU, *EuZW* 2018, 477-484, 482; RACHEL BREWSTER, Can International Trade Law Recover? WTO Dispute Settlement: Can we go back again?, *AJIL UNBOUND*, vol. 113, 2019, 61-66, 64.

⁵⁸ It is noteworthy that Articles 8.2 and 8.3 SG Agreement allow for retaliation in case that negotiations over compensation for safeguard measures fail. It would therefore have been possible to implement retaliatory measures entirely in line with WTO obligations, had the legal procedure been observed. See also JÉRÉMIE CHARLES, Filling the Gap: Are the EU Retaliatory Tariffs Consistent with EU Law?, *Global Trade and Customs Journal*, vol. 13, 2018, 532-538.

⁵⁹ Similar measures introduced by the Bush administration in 2002 as safeguard measures failed to qualify as «safeguards», see e.g. *US – Steel Safeguards*, DS253, Report of the Appellate Body, 10 November 2003.

countermeasures will cause more damage to the national economy than to the importing economy because of the mutual integration in value chains. Chances of success are also relatively low since it has to be assumed that the volume of exports to smaller economies is generally not sufficiently large for losses due to tariff increases to force a larger economy to rethink its trade policy. Finally, since countermeasures must be proportionate and limited to compensation for the damage caused, it is even conceivable that it is not even possible for a small economy to meaningfully compensate for the entire damage through bilateral tariff increases.

Hence, small and independent economies had to rely from the start on the willingness of other WTO members 1) to comply – in principle – with WTO-law voluntarily, and 2) to join forces against non-complying members, e.g. by filing or joining complaints against them.

4. Please, reboot...

With the at least temporary suspension of the WTO appeals procedure, the WTO can no longer fully perform its role as guardian of order in the global market. The dispute settlement system has *de facto* been downgraded to the Panel procedure which had been developing under the GATT (1947): decisions are understood as recommendations and compliance with them is voluntary.⁶⁰ As a result, dispute settlement in global trade is shifting from a legal to a political framework – and thus away from the multilateral forum of the WTO to bilateral negotiations.⁶¹

This is very bad news for small and independent economies as ultimately, the WTO legal framework served to a considerable extent as a counterbalance to economic and power imbalances between WTO members. Without the legal protection of equality and the global minimum standard in trade relations, the protection of trade interests of small and independent economies – particularly in times of a global pandemic – will become tricky, to say the least.

a. Multi-Party Interim Appeal Arbitration Arrangement

In order to achieve a minimum level of legal security and protection in their trade relations, small and independent economies are likely to turn to regional or plurilateral alternatives. In this sense, the initiative of the EU and 22 other WTO members is already well on the way to closing the AB's gap in dispute settlement in international trade matters. The Multi-Party Interim Appeal Arbitration Arrangement (MPIA) provides for an independent appeal body outside the WTO institutions to which disputed WTO panel decisions can be referred to.⁶² This will ensure that the possibility for a review remains available and that such rulings become final. The WTO members which are part of the initiative agree to not refer a WTO Panel ruling to the AB under Article 16.4 DSU – and thus to prevent the ruling from becoming final. Next to the EU, also China, Canada and Brazil are signatories to the MPIA. Hence, for small and independent economies, joining the MPIA in general provides for considerable legal security in trade relations with a potentially still increasing number of smaller and larger economies.

Not part of the MPIA are, however, the US, Russia and India (along with many smaller economies). Depending on the structure of trade relations of a small and independent economy, hence, the MPIA

⁶⁰ MATTHIAS OESCH, Das Streitbelegungsverfahren der WTO, recht 2004 Heft 5, 192-205, 192-3.

⁶¹ It remains conceivable, of course, that WTO members agree to accept the Panel rulings in principle and to not refer the matter to the AB under Article 16.4 DSU. This would ensure that decisions of the WTO dispute settlement body would remain legally binding.

⁶² European Commission, 'The WTO multi-party interim appeal arrangement gets operational', 3 August 2020, <<https://trade.ec.europa.eu/doclib/press/index.cfm?id=2176>>.

will not actually provide for the necessary legal security as long as the number of signatories remains limited.

b. Preferential Trade Agreements

It seems critical – as discussed above – that small and independent economies can reduce their vulnerability with regard to safeguard measures on top of other tariff increases. Regarding the exemption of small and independent economies from unilateral safeguard measures, Preferential Trade Agreements (PTAs) could be an important tool for the legal protection of export industries: The EU exempted, for example, the EEA countries from the safeguard tariffs on steel on the grounds that the risk of trade diversion was low given the close economic integration of the EEA countries. However, the EEA Agreement also explicitly prohibits reciprocal safeguard measures.⁶³ This continues to cause irritation in Switzerland and is the subject of bilateral negotiations in the Joint Committee of the 1972 Free Trade Agreement (FTA 1972) between Switzerland and the European Economic Community. Switzerland is of the opinion that the EU safeguard measures are incompatible with Article 26 in conjunction with Article 27 of the FTA 1972. However, since the FTA 1972 does not provide for a legal dispute settlement procedure next to the political dispute settlement, Switzerland could only file a complaint against the safeguard measures applied by the EU at the WTO.⁶⁴ Turkey has done just that and lodged a complaint against the EU safeguard measures in March 2020.⁶⁵ A Panel is currently being set up. Switzerland, along with a number of other WTO members, reserved third party rights.⁶⁶

Hence, in these circumstances, bilateral and regional PTAs are becoming increasingly important for small and independent economies. They provide additional legal certainty in uncertain times through common, more far-reaching provisions and an additional dispute settlement mechanism. It is therefore in the interest of small economies to conclude PTAs with markets which are of particular importance for their export industries. As has been shown in the pandemic, it is also in the interest of small economies to have PTAs with those markets which supply components for their own industry – or for the protection of public health for that matter.

As the bilateral relationship between the EU and Switzerland shows, it is of great interest, especially for small and independent economies, to provide for a separate dispute settlement mechanism in bilateral or even regional agreements and to prohibit in principle the application of unilateral safeguard measures in the bilateral relationship. As has been shown in the context of the EU measures taken in

⁶³ In 2016, the Swiss Federal Council responded to the question of how the unequal treatment of the Swiss steel industry in relation to the EEA states with regard to monitoring measures is compatible with the Swiss-EU bilateral agreements as follows: «Trade between Switzerland and the EU is regulated by the Free Trade Agreement of 1972. This agreement (in contrast to the EEA agreement) does not prohibit the use of commercial and political protective measures and does not contain any special provisions on trade in steel products. However, according to the agreement, measures that impair imports must meet certain requirements (including protection of overriding public interests, proportionality).» Answer of the Swiss Federal Council of August 17, 2016, Interpellation Sauter, <<https://www.parlament.ch/de/ratsbetrieb/suche-curia-vista/geschaefft?AffairId=20163508>>.

⁶⁴ Free Trade Agreement between Switzerland and the European Economic Community, 22 July 1972; see also CHARLOTTE SIEBER-GASSER, 'Handelsbeziehungen Schweiz – EU im globalen Kontext', *sui-generis* 2020.

⁶⁵ *European Union – Safeguard Measures on Certain Steel Products*, Request for Consultations by Turkey, 19 March 2020, WT/DS595/1.

⁶⁶ The complaint deals with Article XIX GATT and the SG Agreement. Turkey takes issue with the fact that the EU did not in their view sufficiently demonstrate that there had been an unforeseeable increase in imports, which products were specifically affected, and to what extent this represented a serious threat to the EU industry. See WTO, «Panel established to review EU safeguard measures on steel imports», 28 August 2020, <https://www.wto.org/english/news_e/news20_e/dsb_28aug20_e.htm>.

relation to the pandemic – from which Switzerland is exempt – such measures are counterproductive and harmful to all parties involved if mutual economic integration is sufficiently comprehensive.⁶⁷

The legal remedies usually provided for in PTAs are not much different from existing WTO remedies, but because PTAs generally provide for additional preferences beyond the WTO minimum standard and cover additional fields of interest outside of the scope of WTO agreements, infringements can be compensated in a bilateral agreement by small economies more easily than in a global context. Furthermore, a dispute settlement procedure in a bilateral relationship in principle obliges both parties to respect each other's obligations anyway – and to implement the potential panel decision.

Finally, strengthening preferentialism can contribute to the promotion of a new global consensus on the evolution of global trade rules: Through the so-called «spaghetti bowl»-effect, even small economies can influence the future shape of global trade rules.⁶⁸

c. ... loading system updates?

In new or re-negotiated PTAs involving small and independent economies, the parties should accordingly agree on a course of action with regard to the WTO dispute settlement proceedings. This could be 1) a commitment to first resort to the procedure provided for in the PTA, 2) a commitment to accept a possible WTO Panel ruling, or 3) a commitment to join the MPIA until the WTO has an appeal body again.

In addition, a potential reform of the WTO dispute settlement proceedings would ideally take into account the fact that small economies have in the past had little or not opportunity to defend themselves against infringements by large economic blocs. This shortcoming from the point of view of small and independent economies could be remedied, for example by either 1) allowing safeguard measures to be taken only against the states responsible for trade diversion (i.e. moving away from the principle of unilateral safeguard measures) or 2) «multilateralising» countermeasures, i.e. allowing all WTO members – rather than only the complainants — to take appropriate countermeasures once a breach of WTO obligations has been established.

Finally, a regulatory mechanism could be envisaged which would allow WTO members to act more immediately on the imposition of duties which appear to be in breach without having to wait for the conclusion of the dispute settlement proceedings. This last point appears particularly critical, especially since – as has been shown here –, a large number of the recent tariff increases and respective pending WTO disputes revolve around the «waiting period» between harmful, potentially illegal trade measure and the panel decision. Revision of Article 23 DSU would not only strengthen the position of small and independent economies in the WTO, but also help resolve some of the current tensions between large economic blocs.

⁶⁷ Communication from the Commission (2020/C911/02), 20 March 2020, para. 4.2: «in view of the deep integration of the internal market with all four member States of the European Free Trade Association (EFTA), as well as the integration of the production value chains and distribution networks with the same countries, the Implementing Regulation does not apply to exports to those four countries, which thus remain unrestricted.» There is also a certain contradiction here with the previous EU policy criticized by Switzerland with regard to safeguard measures on steel.

⁶⁸ THOMAS COTTIER/CHARLOTTE SIEBER-GASSER/GABRIELA WERMELINGER, 'The Dialectical Relationship of Preferentialism and Multilateralism', In: M. Elsig and A. Dür (eds.), *Trade Cooperation: The Purpose, Design and Effects of Preferential Trade Agreements*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2015, 465-495.